

Synthesis and Characterisation of Tritelluratocobaltate(III) Complex

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Tellurium(VI) in tellurate can function as a heteropoly addendum, like periodate. Furthermore, tellurate ion is a good oxidising as well as stabilising agent. It can stabilise, like periodate, unusual oxidation states of many transition metal ions. The object of the study is how far tellurate group can behave as addendum, like periodate which can easily form derivatives having organic ligands and can undergo condensation and co-condensation into cross-linked or linear polymers via polyfunctional ligands.

Lister and Yoshino prepared cobalt(III) tellurate of 1 : 2 type. This inspired us to prepare cobalt(III) tellurate of 1 : 3 type as $K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$ in strong alkaline medium. The compound has been characterised by various physicochemical studies, e.g. chemical analyses, thermal analyses, oxidation state determination, magnetic moment measurement, electronic and infrared spectral studies and powder X-ray studies. The probable structure of the compound has also been suggested.

TELLURIUM(VI) in tellurate can function as a heteropoly addendum, like periodate; because it has got a small size, a high positive charge and ability to take tetrahedral and octahedral geometry with oxygen. Furthermore, tellurate ion is a good oxidising as well as stabilising agent. It can stabilise unusual oxidation states of many transition metal ions¹⁻³, like periodate. Our object is to study how far tellurate group can behave as addendum, like periodate which can easily form derivatives having organic ligands and can undergo condensation and co-condensation into cross-linked or linear polymers via polyfunctional ligands.

A number of cobalt(III) periodato compounds were reported by different workers⁴⁻⁶. Lister and Yoshino⁷ prepared cobalt(III) tellurate (1 : 2 type) as $K_3H_6Co(TeO_6)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$. These inspired us to prepare cobalt(III) tellurato compound (1 : 3 type) as $K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$ in strong alkaline medium. The compound has been characterised by various physicochemical studies to elucidate its probable structure.

Experimental

Cobalt chloride (1.19 g, 0.005 mol) was mixed with telluric acid (2.29 g, 0.01 mol) in water (450 ml). Potassium hydroxide (34 g, 0.60 mol) dissolved in water (50 ml) was added to the mixture. Immediately solution of potassium hypochlorite (30 ml, 0.02 mol) was added with stirring. A dark green colour appeared in the solution and an olive-green solid

was formed. The solution was filtered through sintered bed crucible and the solid was discarded. The solution on treatment with one-half of its own volume of ethanol, added in small amounts and with constant stirring, precipitated a dark green compound. The precipitate was dissolved in water (100 ml) and 4 M potassium hydroxide solution (100 ml) was added. After standing overnight, the dark green compound was collected on a sintered bed crucible, and washed several times with water, four times with 50% ethanol-water mixture and two times with absolute ethanol. The compound was dried over fused calcium chloride desiccator for 24 h, (0.72 g) (Found: K, 12.94; Co, 6.36; Te, 42.61; H_2O , 4.03. Calcd: K, 13.10; Co, 6.58; Te, 42.77; H_2O , 4.02%).

Tellurium was estimated gravimetrically⁸ as metallic tellurium by reduction with 50% hydroxylamine hydrochloride in sulphur dioxide medium after proper dissolution of the complex. Cobalt was estimated⁹ as cobalt α -nitroso- β -naphthol complex, weighed as $CoSO_4$. Potassium was determined in a Varian Techtron AA6 spectrophotometer. Water was determined from weight loss at 120° for 4 h. The oxidation state of the compound was determined iodometrically⁴.

The thermogram of the compound was recorded with a Simadzu DT-30 thermal analyser at the rate of 10° min⁻¹ from room temperature 30 to 700° in nitrogen atmosphere. DTA was also recorded with the same instrument at the same time. The magnetic moment was measured at room temperature by

TABLE 1—THERMAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF $K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$

Reaction	Temp., °C		Total wt. loss : Found/(Calcd.)	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
	TGA	DTA		K	Co	Te
$K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3] \cdot 2H_2O$ $\rightarrow K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3]$ $+ 2 H_2O$	80-95	95	35.80 (36.00)	13.82 (13.65)	6.55 (6.86)	43.86 (44.56)
$K_3[Co(H_4TeO_6)_3]$ $\rightarrow K_3CoTe_3O_{12} + 6 H_2O$	95-325	—	143.20 (144.00)	16.04 (15.61)	7.48 (8.84)	50.82 (50.97)
$K_3CoTe_3O_{12} \rightarrow$ $3/2 K_2O + 1/3 Co_2O_3$ $+ 8 TeO_3 + 19/6 [O]$	325-700	675	194.95 (194.00)	17.54 (16.74)	8.09 (8.41)	53.70 (54.66)

Gouy magnetic balance using $CuSO_4 \cdot 5H_2O$ as calibrant. The reflectance spectrum was recorded in a Cary 17D spectrophotometer using $MgCO_3$ as adsorbent in the range 200-800 nm. Ir spectrum was recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 357 spectrophotometer using CsI phase in the range 4000-200 cm^{-1} . X-Ray photograph was recorded in a Guineer camera using K_α radiation.

Results and Discussion

Thermal analysis : The results of the thermal analysis (Table 1) reveal that the first step of decomposition (30-95°) involves release of water of crystallisation loosely bound to the compound. The peak found from DTA curve is 95°. The second step of decomposition (95-325°) involves the loss of six molecules of feebly coordinated water molecules with the formation of an intermediate compound $K_3CoTe_3O_{12}$, which was found to be somewhat stable from 325 to 435°. The composition of the intermediate compounds have been confirmed by their chemical analyses (Table 1). The compound was further decomposed at ~ 435° with the formation of Co_2O_3 , K_2O and TeO_3 as final end-products. DTA curve shows a peak at 675° for this decomposition.

Oxidation state : Oxidation state of the compound determined iodometrically⁴, showed the trivalency of cobalt and hexavalency of tellurium. The following reaction indicates that the tritellurato-cobaltate require 7-equivalents of thiosulphate to titrate the liberated iodine per mole of the compound corresponding to the reaction of cobalt(III) to cobalt(II) and tellurate to tellurite.

Magnetic moment : Magnetic measurement of the compound shows that it is slightly paramagnetic ($\mu_{eff} = 1.023$ B.M.) but actually the compound should be diamagnetic. This is due to the presence of some cobalt(II) ions in the compound⁵.

Absorption spectra : The reflectance spectrum shows that the compound has got very low solubility in water and in other solvents. So the electronic spectrum was recorded with the dark green mother liquor in KOH using the same spectrophotometer.

The reflectance spectrum of the compound is characterised by four characteristic bands at 220, 250, 370 and 625 nm. The band at 220 nm is characteristic of a TeO_6 octahedron. The high intensity band at 250 nm is due to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition of the ligand¹⁰. The bands which appeared at 370 and 625 nm are due to the d-d transitions¹¹, $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$, respectively as expected for a spin-paired six-coordinated cobalt(III) octahedral complex.

There is no appreciable change in the electronic spectral curve of the solution. This indicates that the complex retains its six-coordinated octahedral environment both in solid state and in solution.

Infrared spectra : The broad band that appears at 3700-3450 cm^{-1} is due to the valency stretching vibration of the Te-OH and stretching vibration of -OH group. The broadening is probably due to the overlap of the ν_{OH} of the lattice water¹². The band at 2300 cm^{-1} is in agreement with that of the first harmonic of Te-OH deformation band at 1210 cm^{-1} . The bands at 1625 and 1490 cm^{-1} are attributed to the O-H deformation of water molecule. The band at 1075 cm^{-1} is due to Te-OH deformation mode having harmonic at 2300 cm^{-1} . The band appearing at 1027 cm^{-1} is due to Te-OH deformation mode. The band at 725 cm^{-1} is due to Te-O valence stretching vibration.

The band appearing at 520 cm^{-1} can be assigned to M-O stretching vibration¹³ and at 430 cm^{-1} is due to O-Te-O deformation vibration (as compared to O-I-O)¹⁴. The absorption at 340 cm^{-1} is due to δ_{O-M-O} and δ_{M-O-Te} bridging¹⁵. Variations at 260, 240 and 220 cm^{-1} are due to lattice vibrations¹⁶.

TABLE 2—INTERPLANAR SPACINGS OF COMPOUND

d Å	Intensity	d Å	Intensity
5.1650	w	3.2215	m
4.8465	s(b)	3.1056	w
4.6204	w	2.9502	s(b)
4.2965	vw	2.6421	vw
4.1028	m	2.4512	w
3.5520	w	1.9601	mw
3.4892	s(b)	1.6542	w

w = weak, s = strong, b = broad, v = very, m = medium.

Powder X-ray study : The interplanar spacings with intensities, obtained from the powder X-ray studies, are tabulated in Table 2.

Structure : Considering the physicochemical studies of the compound, the probable structure of the anionic part of the compound is given below.

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